

DRUM

Drivers of Resistance in Uganda & Malawi

Standard Operating Procedure	Version: 2
River water sample collection and analysis for samples included in the DRUM study.	
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Version History

Version	Date	Comment
1.0	01/04/19	Initial version
2.0	01/07/19	Changes after initial pilot phase

1. Introduction

This method is applicable to the collection of river water samples included in the DRUM study.

The proportion of patients admitted to hospitals in Uganda and Malawi with invasive infections caused by ESBL resistant Enterobacteriaceae including ESBL E coli (ESBL-E) and ESBL K pneumoniae (ESBL-K) is increasing. Given the reduced availability of Carbapenems, many of these drug-resistant infections are locally untreatable. To understand the drivers of this antimicrobial resistance, further evidence of the role of household environment contamination on human and animal carriage with ESBL-E and ESBL-K is required.

2. Purpose

This method of collection and filtration will be used to obtain cultured ESBL and non-ESBL *E. coli* / *K. pneumoniae* isolates from water.

3. Responsibilities

- Field workers
 - Collection of human and animal stool, and environmental samples in according to Sample Collection SOPs
 - Correct labelling of collection samples
 - Prompt transport of collected samples to the laboratory
 - Completion of sample collection log
- Core Laboratory Technicians
 - Receive samples from field and complete sample collection log
 - Register samples on DRUM telepath eLIMS system
 - Inform Study Laboratory Technicians of sample arrival
- Study Laboratory Technicians
 - Ensure prompt collection of study samples from laboratory reception
 - Double-check correct sample labelling
 - Processing stool samples in accordance with this SOP
 - Storage of samples for further analysis in accordance with this SOP
- Principal Investigators
 - Ensure laboratory training in sample processing procedures provided
 - Undertake quality control checks of laboratory processing.

4. Procedure

4.1 Materials needed

Gloves

Autoclavable Nalgene bottles

Sterile collection bags

Hand disinfectant

GPS coordinator

Dissolved Oxygen Monitor

pH monitor

- All river water samples should be chosen by the field staff in relation to areas where households access river water for drinking, cooking, cleaning, fishing or playing (SOP3).
- A dynamic risk assessment of the area should be undertaken by the field staff to ensure it is safe to approach and sample from the river. If access is impeded, or it is decided that it is unsafe to approach, then the river sampling can be abandoned.
- Once a river site has been deemed safe, and an accurate reflection of the location used by the household, this should be GPS located.
- Other parameters should be identified, including water pH, dissolved oxygen concentration, temperature, turbidity, depth, colour and an assessment of the river flow rate. These should be logged onto the collection form.
- A sample of river water should be collected aseptically in pre-autoclaved 500ml or 1L Nalgene bottles. Care should be taken when opening the bottle not to contaminate the inside.
- The bottle should be submerged into the water, with the hand of the fieldworker placed behind the flow of the water.
- Where possible a total volume of 500mL should be obtained, and reasons for collection of <500mL should be stated on the electronic record.
- After labelling, place the bottle in a container away from light for transport to the laboratory (section 5).

5. Sample Receipt and Storage

Protect all samples from direct sunlight and transport in an insulated container or refrigerator at 2 – 8°C. Samples should be analysed as soon as is practicable and storage under the above conditions should not exceed 12 h before the commencement of analysis.

7. Health and Safety

Please refer to risk assessment tools and local health and safety guidelines

